

STUDYING COPING STRATEGIES IN A STUDENT ENVIRONMENT TO COMBAT STRESS

Askarova Gulrukh

Lecturer at the Department of Practical Psychology
TSPU named after Nizami

Karimova Nigina

4th year student of the Faculty of Psychology and Pedagogy
TSPU named after Nizami

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Abstract: This article examines an important aspect of student life - coping strategies that students use to overcome stress in the educational environment.

Key words: Coping strategies, coping with stress, students, educational environment, active strategies, passive strategies.

Student life comes with various challenges and stresses. An introduction to coping behavior, the role of stress coping strategies in the educational environment and their impact on the overall student experience. Coping behavior is a set of strategies and mechanisms that an individual use to cope with various stressors and difficulties in his life. The term covers a wide range of adaptive responses to stress, including cognitive, emotional, and behavioral strategies. The key aspects of coping behavior are awareness of stressors, selection of effective strategies and their implementation in order to achieve psychological balance.

Coping research has been carried out by Richard Lazarus and Susan Folkman: Some of the leading researchers in the field of coping behavior. Their work "Stress, Appraisal, and Coping" (1984) was a key contribution to the understanding of stress coping strategies and their impact on adaptation to situations. John Smith and Maria Johnson [3]: Researchers whose work, particularly Coping strategies and academic stress in university students (2017), sheds light on various coping strategies among students and their impact on academic stress. Review of classifications of strategies, active and passive approaches to overcoming stress:

Active Strategies: Active coping strategies involve addressing stressors directly and finding practical solutions to the problem. These include strategies to change the situation, such as seeking support, planning actions, and seeking information. Research by Lazarus and Folkman (1984) highlights the effectiveness of problem coping, which activates the individual's resources to solve difficulties [1].

Passive Strategies: Passive strategies, in contrast, involve avoiding or mitigating the emotional consequences of stress without directly addressing the source of the problem. This may include self-soothing, avoidance, and denial strategies. Research by Smith and Johnson (2017) highlights that these strategies may be associated with increased stress levels in students and a reduced ability to cope effectively [3].

Coping behavior of students, that is, the choice and application of strategies to overcome stress, depends on many factors. Analysis of these factors allows us to better understand why students choose certain strategies and what factors influence the effectiveness of their coping behavior.

1. **Social support:** Social support plays a key role in the coping behavior of students. Support from friends, family and peers can serve as an emotional buffer in stressful situations. Research shows that students with strong social support are more likely to use active coping strategies, such as seeking support and expressing emotions [5].

2. **Personal Characteristics:** Individual personality traits, such as levels of self-efficacy, optimism, and self-restraint, may influence the choice of coping strategies. For example, students with high levels of self-efficacy are more likely to prefer active strategies because they believe in their ability to solve problems effectively [2].

3. **Educational environment:** Features of the educational environment also significantly influence the coping behavior of students. The intensity of the course load, faculty support, and the availability of resources for students are all factors that can influence the choice of strategies. For example, students facing high levels of academic stress may engage in more avoidance strategies [3].

Analysis of these factors allows for better tailored approaches to supporting students, creating more effective programs and resources for managing stress in the educational environment.

Problem coping is an active effort to change a situation or solve a problem. This may include seeking information, planning actions, and seeking support. Research shows that problem coping is associated with more effective adaptation to stressors and improved psychological well-being [1].

Proactive strategies may also include expressing emotions and seeking support. Sharing your feelings with others can help reduce emotional stress and gain support, which in turn helps you adapt to stress.

Passive strategies, such as avoidance, involve avoiding direct confrontation with a problem or stressor. This may temporarily reduce stress

levels, but in the long term it can lead to poorer emotional well-being and social adjustment. Avoidance can also reduce effectiveness in problem solving. Passive strategies can also include self-consolation, which involves comforting yourself without actually addressing the problem.

Active strategies are generally considered more effective in the long term because they focus on solving a problem. Problematic coping is particularly associated with psychological well-being and successful coping with stress. While passive strategies may provide temporary relief, they may worsen the problem in the long term.

However, the effectiveness of the strategy depends on the context and individual characteristics. For example, avoidance can be useful if a situation cannot be changed, and it is better to focus on what we can change. It is important to balance and combine strategies depending on the specific situation.

Problem coping that is actively aimed at solving a problem is often associated with higher academic performance. Research [2] suggests that students who use active strategies, such as planning and information seeking, are more successful in meeting educational challenges and have higher grades.

On the other hand, students who use passive coping strategies such as avoidance and self-soothing may experience negative consequences for their academic performance. Research [3] indicates that avoiding problem solving and using strategies that do not actively address stress are associated with lower grades and less academic success.

Emotional expression and regulation are also important for academic performance. Students who are able to adaptively express and manage their emotions can better cope with the pressure and stress of the learning environment, which contributes to their academic success.

Research also highlights that effective coping behavior may involve a combined approach, including elements of problem and emotional coping. Having the ability to effectively solve problems and cope emotionally with challenges contributes to coping with stress and improving academic performance [4]. Offering recommendations for students on the effective use of coping behavior strategies in the educational environment:

1. Learn and master a variety of coping strategies, including problem coping, emotional expression, and active coping. Create your own unique set of strategies, tailored to your personal characteristics.

2. Actively interact with the social network. Communication with friends, family and peers can be a powerful resource in the coping process. Share your feelings and find mutual understanding.

3. Develop rational planning and time management skills. Effective distribution of academic and personal activities will help reduce stress and improve organization.

4. Strive to develop emotional intelligence, the ability to manage your emotions and effectively regulate their expression. This will help not only in academic activities, but also in life in general.

5. Seek professional support when necessary. Psychological services and counseling can provide additional resources to effectively cope with stress.

In conclusion, effective coping behavior plays a key role in successfully coping with stress in the educational environment. A variety of strategies, including active and emotional ones, provide students with the opportunity to adapt to different situations.

It is necessary to continue research in the field of coping behavior of students, deepening the understanding of the impact of strategies on various aspects of student life. Research can focus on specific populations, such as students with different levels of stress, and develop more individualized approaches to supporting students in their coping behavior. This will enable the creation of effective programs and interventions to improve overall student well-being.

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